

Supplementary Material for "Forward Only Learning for Orthogonal Neural Networks of any Depth"

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A Detailed Experimental Setup and Hyperparameters

In this section, we provide a comprehensive overview of the experimental setup and hyperparameters used in our study, detailing the conditions under which *FOTON* is evaluated. This includes the architectures, datasets, and training protocols chosen to highlight its practical performance compared to standard backpropagation and other forward-only baselines.

Unless otherwise specified, the orthogonalization rate is set to 1 and the number of Björck iterations used to orthogonalize the weights is fixed to 5. In the same way, unless otherwise specified, F is updated once per epoch to keep the weight mirroring assumption valid. The experiments were run on a single A100 GPU.

Table 1 shows the hyperparameters used for the 1, 2, and 3 hidden layers networks, Table 2 shows the hyperparameters used for the 5, 10 and 50 hidden layers networks and Table 3 shows the hyperparameters used for the convolutional networks.

Table 1: 1, 2, and 3 hidden layers network architectures and settings used in the experiments.

Hyperparameters	1 Hidden layer			2 Hidden layers			3 Hidden layers		
Dataset	MNIST	CIFAR10	CIFAR100	MNIST	CIFAR10	CIFAR100	MNIST	CIFAR10	CIFAR100
Input size	$28 \times 28 \times 1$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$	$28 \times 28 \times 1$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$	$28 \times 28 \times 1$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$
Hidden units	1×1024	1×1024	1×1024	2×1024	2×1024	2×1024	3×1024	3×1024	3×1024
Output units	10	10	100	10	10	100	10	10	100
Learning rate BP	0.1	0.01	0.1	0.1	0.01	0.1	0.1	0.01	0.1
Learning rate PEPITA	0.1	0.2	0.01	0.1	0.01	0.01	0.001	0.01	0.01
Learning rate FOTON	0.2	0.05	0.05	0.2	0.05	0.05	0.1	0.05	0.05
Weight decay BP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Weight decay PEPITA	10^{-5}	10^{-4}	10^{-5}	10^{-5}	10^{-4}	10^{-5}	10^{-5}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}
Weight decay FOTON	0	0	0	10^{-2}	10^{-1}	0	0	0	10^{-3}
Batch size BP	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64
Batch size PEPITA	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64
Batch size FOTON	256	256	256	256	256	256	256	256	256
Number of Epochs	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Dropout BP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dropout PEPITA	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Dropout FOTON	0	0.1	0.2	0	0.2	0.2	0	0	0
Error PEPITA	MSE								
Error FOTON	MSE	CE	CE	MSE	CE	CE	MSE	CE	CE
CE temperature		4	1		4	1		1	2
Decay epochs BP	None								
Decay epochs PEPITA	60, 90	60, 90	60, 90	60, 90	60, 90	60, 90	60, 90	60, 90	60, 90
Decay epochs FOTON	None								

In the first case reported Table 1, we used a hidden size of 1024 hidden units, either for 1, 2, or 3 hidden layers, and the output size was 10 for MNIST and CIFAR10, and 100 for CIFAR100. In the second case reported in Table 2, we used a hidden size of 256 units, and the output size was 10 for MNIST and CIFAR10, and 100 for CIFAR100. In the third case reported in Table 3, we used one or two convolutional layer with 32 filters of size 3×3 followed by a linear layer, after each convolution we applied a rescaled average pooling and the output size was 10 for MNIST and 100 for CIFAR100. The BP baseline was trained using standard SGD optimizer. The ReLU non linearity was used between every layer in every setting. However, for the deeper architecture with 50 layers we replaced ReLU with TanH, since preliminary trials showed that TanH helped mitigate the dying ReLU effect and consistently provided better results in terms of both convergence and final accuracy.

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Table 2: 5, 10 and 50 hidden layers network architectures and settings used in the experiments.

Hyperparameters	5 Hidden layers			10 Hidden layers			50 Hidden layers		
Dataset	MNIST	CIFAR10	CIFAR100	MNIST	CIFAR10	CIFAR100	MNIST	CIFAR10	CIFAR100
Input size	$28 \times 28 \times 1$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$	$28 \times 28 \times 1$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$	$28 \times 28 \times 1$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$
Output units	10	10	100	10	10	100	10	10	100
Learning rate BP	0.1	0.01	0.1	0.1	0.01	0.1	0.01	0.01	0.01
Learning rate FOTON	0.2	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.1	0.005	0.005
Weight decay BP	0	0	0	0	0	0	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}
Weight decay FOTON	0	0	10^{-4}	0	0	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}
Batch size BP	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64
Batch size FOTON	256	256	256	256	256	256	256	256	256
Number of Epochs	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Dropout BP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dropout FOTON	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Error FOTON	MSE	CE	CE	MSE	CE	CE	MSE	CE	CE
CE temperature		1	2		2	2		2	2
Decay epochs BP	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60
Decay epochs FOTON	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60	30,60

Table 3: 1 and 2 convolutional layers followed by a 1 linear layer classifier head architectures and settings used in the experiments.

Hyperparameters	1 convolutional layer		2 convolutional layers	
Dataset	MNIST	CIFAR100	MNIST	CIFAR100
Input size	$28 \times 28 \times 1$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$	$28 \times 28 \times 1$	$32 \times 32 \times 3$
Output units	10	100	10	100
Learning rate BP				
Learning rate FOTON	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.01
Weight decay BP	0	0	0	0
Weight decay FOTON	0	0	0	0
Batch size BP	64	64	64	64
Batch size FOTON	256	256	256	256
Number of Epochs	100	100	100	100
Dropout BP	0	0	0	0
Dropout FOTON	0	0	0	0
Error FOTON	CE	CE	CE	CE
CE temperature	1	1	2	1
Decay epochs BP	None	None	None	None
Decay epochs FOTON	None	None	None	None

B Theoretical comparison between FOTON and Backpropagation

In this section we prove in details that FOTON gives a first order approximation of the exact gradient computed by Backpropagation.

B.1 Equivalence in deep linear regime

We start showing the simplified result in the case of deep linear networks that are neural networks without activation functions. These models are just a composition of linear functions and therefore they do not have any approximation advantage over a linear regression, however they differ in the optimization dynamics and while PEPITA, and its variants, match backpropagation in the linear regression case they differ from exact gradient computation on linear deep neural networks. We show that FOTON computes exactly the gradients in this case and experiments support our theoretical findings. We believe that the simplified case will make more clear the role of orthogonality and of FOTON’s learning rule.

Theorem B.1 (Equivalence in deep linear regime). *In the case of deep linear neural networks, FOTON perfectly matches backpropagation, i.e.*

$$\delta W_\ell^{FO} = \delta W_\ell^{BP} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial W_\ell} \quad \forall \ell = 1, \dots, L$$

Proof. We start recalling the update of backpropagation:

$$\delta W_\ell^{BP} = -\eta \delta a_\ell^{BP} (h_{\ell-1})^\top \quad \text{for } 1 \leq \ell < L; \quad (1)$$

$$\delta W_L^{BP} = -\eta e h_{L-1}^\top. \quad (2)$$

It follows that FOTON is equivalent to backpropagation if and only if $\delta a_\ell^{FO} = \delta a_\ell^{BP}$ for all ℓ . The two recursive formulas can be expanded as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta a_\ell^{FO} &= W_\ell \sigma_{\ell-1} (W_{\ell-1} \sigma_{\ell-2} (\dots \sigma_1 (W_1 x))) - W_\ell \sigma_{\ell-1} (W_{\ell-1} \sigma_{\ell-2} (\dots \sigma_1 (W_1 (x - Fe)))) \\ \delta a_\ell^{BP} &= \sigma'_\ell W_{\ell+1}^\top \sigma'_{\ell+1} \dots W_L^\top e \end{aligned}$$

In the linear case, that is when the activation function are the identity, the two become:

$$\begin{aligned}\delta a_\ell^{FO} &= W_\ell(W_{\ell-1}(\cdots W_1 x)) - W_\ell(W_{\ell-1}(\cdots W_1(x - Fe))) \\ \delta a_\ell^{BP} &= W_{\ell+1}^\top W_{\ell+2}^\top \cdots W_L^\top e\end{aligned}$$

When the weight matrices are row-orthogonal, the first update of FOTON is the following:

$$\delta a_\ell^{FO} = W_\ell(W_{\ell-1}(\cdots W_1 Fe))$$

and admitting a perfect weight alignment, as implemented in FOTON, since $F = W_1^\top W_2^\top \cdots W_L^\top$, we have:

$$\delta a_\ell^{FO} = W_\ell(W_{\ell-1}(\cdots W_1 W_1^\top W_2^\top \cdots W_L^\top) e) = W_{\ell+1}^\top W_{\ell+2}^\top \cdots W_L^\top e = \delta a_\ell^{BP}$$

and the proof is complete. \square

B.2 Equivalence in deep norm-preserving regime

FOTON may perfectly match backpropagation in a more general and interesting case than the previously discussed linear one but at the cost of a bigger memory consumption. This will not make FOTON a valuable alternative to the better performing backpropagation but it shows a closer gap to exact gradient computation with respect to PEPITA.

Theorem B.2. *Let f be an orthogonal neural network with piecewise orthogonal (and linear) activation functions, such as GroupSort. We assume that the non-linear activations are incorporated in the matrix F as*

$$F = W_1^\top \sigma'_1 W_2^\top \sigma'_2 \cdots W_L^\top$$

where the gradient of the activation functions are taken in the respective activation h_ℓ obtained from the standard forward pass of x . In this case FOTON is exactly equivalent to backpropagation, i.e.

$$\delta W_\ell^{FO} = \delta W_\ell^{BP} \quad \forall \ell$$

Proof. The proof is similar to the one given in B.1 with some additional details to take care of. First of all, the error e can be considered small compared to x , i.e. $\|Fe\| \ll \|x\|$. We can thus assume that the activation patterns by x do not change from those by $x - Fe$ and so we have that

$$\begin{aligned}\delta a_\ell^{FO} &= W_\ell \sigma_{\ell-1}(W_{\ell-1} \sigma_{\ell-2}(\cdots \sigma_1(W_1 x))) - W_\ell \sigma_{\ell-1}(W_{\ell-1} \sigma_{\ell-2}(\cdots \sigma_1(W_1(x - Fe)))) \\ &= W_\ell \sigma_{\ell-1}(W_{\ell-1} \sigma_{\ell-2}(\cdots \sigma_1(W_1(Fe))))\end{aligned}$$

and thus we have

$$\begin{aligned}\delta a_\ell^{FO} &= W_\ell \sigma_{\ell-1}(W_{\ell-1} \sigma_{\ell-2}(\cdots \sigma_1 W_1 W_1^\top \sigma'_1 W_2^\top \sigma'_2 \cdots \sigma'_{L-1} W_L^\top) e) \\ &= \sigma'_\ell W_{\ell+1}^\top \sigma'_{\ell+1} \cdots \sigma'_{L-1} W_L^\top e \\ &= \delta a_\ell^{BP}\end{aligned}$$

since the activation σ_ℓ are piecewise orthogonal $\forall \ell$. \square

Remark B.3. The main issue with the previous theorem is that the gradients w.r.t the activations depend on the single data points. Therefore in order to implement this version, we need to store a matrix F for any data point (or equivalently a tensor of size the dimension of F times the batch size) obtaining an algorithm with a memory cost comparable to backpropagation. A main advantage of FOTON is to have a memory cost independent of the batch size in the error projection, which is a major advantage in the case of large batch sizes.

B.3 Linear approximation in deep non-linear regime

In the case of non-linear networks, there is no guarantee for FOTON to match backpropagation. However some approximations allow us to see how it can still approach backpropagation and make the model learn.

Let f be an orthogonal neural network with any non-linear activation functions σ_ℓ . If we approximate the activation functions linearly ($\sigma_\ell(x) \approx \lambda x$), we get:

$$\begin{aligned}\delta h_\ell^{FO} &= \sigma_\ell(W_\ell \sigma_{\ell-1}(W_{\ell-1} \sigma_{\ell-2}(\cdots \sigma_1(W_1 x)))) - \sigma_\ell(W_\ell \sigma_{\ell-1}(W_{\ell-1} \sigma_{\ell-2}(\cdots \sigma_1(W_1(x - Fe)))))) \\ &\approx \lambda W_\ell \lambda W_{\ell-1} \lambda \cdots \lambda W_1 Fe \\ &= \lambda^\ell \cdot W_{\ell+1}^\top W_{\ell+2}^\top \cdots W_L^\top \nabla_L \mathcal{L}\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\delta h_\ell^{BP} = W_{\ell+1}^\top \sigma'_{\ell+1} \cdots W_L^\top e \approx \lambda^{L-\ell-1} \cdot W_{\ell+1}^\top W_{\ell+2}^\top \cdots W_L^\top \nabla_L \mathcal{L}$$

This leads to:

$$\delta h_\ell^{FO} \approx \lambda^{2\ell-L+1} \cdot \delta h_\ell^{BP}$$

This indicates that the FOTON learning rule can still provide a descent direction in the non-linear case. This is further confirmed in our experiments, where FOTON performs close to backpropagation in many different settings.

C Extension of FOTON to Convolutional Networks

As mentioned in the main text, the application of FOTON to convolutional networks is non-trivial, as the orthogonality constraint is applied to the Toeplitz matrix and not to the convolutional kernel. In the original PEPITA paper [1], a seminal proposition to update convolutional layers relying on forward-only algorithm was made. The kernels are learned based on post and pre-synaptic related terms and the update is computed for each filter. When writing the convolutional layer as a linear operation (the corresponding matrix is a concatenation of doubly Toeplitz matrices as shown by Yi [2]), this update does not match the original PEPITA update, as the update is not computed on the kernel indices but on the kernel patches. In FOTON, we propose to apply the same update as in the fully connected layers. We designed the convolutional update of FOTON to match backpropagation in the linear (or piecewise linear) case as in section B.1. In this section, we first recall the update rule for backpropagation and derive the update rule for FOTON, using the analogy built in section B.1.

For an MLP, BP updates the parameters as: $\delta W_\ell = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial W_\ell} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}(W_\ell h_{l-1})}{\partial W_\ell} = \delta a_\ell h_{l-1}^T$, where \mathcal{L} is the loss function. This follows from the fact that

$$\begin{aligned} \partial \mathcal{L}((W_\ell + \mathcal{E})h_{l-1}) &= \partial \mathcal{L}(W_\ell h_{l-1}) + \left\langle \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial W_\ell h_{l-1}}, \mathcal{E} h_{l-1} \right\rangle + o(\|\mathcal{E}\|) \\ &= \partial \mathcal{L}(W_\ell h_{l-1}) + \left\langle \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial W_\ell h_{l-1}} h_{l-1}^T, \mathcal{E} \right\rangle + o(\|\mathcal{E}\|) \end{aligned}$$

and the result follows from the definition of differential.

In the case of convolutional layers, the $W_\ell h_{l-1}$ is replaced by the convolution $k_\ell * h_{l-1}$ where k_ℓ is the kernel. It follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}((k_\ell + \mathcal{E}) * h_{l-1}) &= \mathcal{L}(k_\ell * h_{l-1}) + \left\langle \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial k_\ell * h_{l-1}}, \mathcal{E} * h_{l-1} \right\rangle + o(\|\mathcal{E}\|) \\ &= \mathcal{L}(W_\ell * h_{l-1}) + \left\langle \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial W_\ell * h_{l-1}}, h_{l-1} * \mathcal{E} \right\rangle + o(\|\mathcal{E}\|) \\ &= \mathcal{L}(W_\ell * h_{l-1}) + \left\langle \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial W_\ell * h_{l-1}}, \text{conv}_{h_{l-1}}(\mathcal{E}) \right\rangle + o(\|\mathcal{E}\|) \\ &= \mathcal{L}(W_\ell * h_{l-1}) + \left\langle \text{conv}_{h_{l-1}}^* \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial W_\ell * h_{l-1}} \right), \mathcal{E} \right\rangle + o(\|\mathcal{E}\|) \end{aligned}$$

where $\text{conv}_k(x) = k * x$ is the left-convolution by a fixed kernel k . Since it's a linear operator, it admits an adjoint, the *transposed convolution*, that we denote by \star . It follows that the update rule for the kernel in backpropagation is:

$$\delta k_\ell = \text{conv}_{h_{l-1}}^*(\delta a_\ell)$$

To match BP in the linear and piecewise linear case, FOTON updates the kernel as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta k_\ell &= \text{conv}_{h_{l-1}}^*(\delta a_\ell^{FO}) \\ &= \text{conv}_{h_{l-1}}^*(a_\ell - a_\ell^{err}) \end{aligned}$$

In practice, the $\text{conv}_{h_\ell}^*$ operator corresponds to the `torch.nn.grad.conv2d_input` function in PyTorch.

D Choice of Pooling Module

Pooling modules are important parts of convolutional neural networks and they are often considered as non linear activations so the theory developed in B.3 applies identically. Max pooling and average pooling are among the most used pooling modules. Adapting max pooling to any forward-only learning system, is however not straightforward. The nature of max pooling itself, which selects the maximum value from a set of inputs and discards the rest is inherently non-differentiable. Handling its selective nature and data-dependency cannot be done only by keeping track of the maximum value as is done in backpropagation.

The alternative we used is average pooling, which is differentiable more compatible with FOTON's forward-only error-driven modulation. Average pooling is linear and row orthogonal if scaled by $\sqrt{2}$, which we implemented to keep the FOTON's orthogonality constraint.

However, it is important to note that in practice, max pooling tends to outperform average pooling in terms of performance in most computer vision tasks, particularly in image classification tasks with datasets such as CIFAR10 and CIFAR100. Adapting max-pooling to FOTON could be a potential future research direction, as it would align better with the standard practice in the field.

References

- [1] G. DellaFerra and G. Kreiman. Error-driven input modulation: solving the credit assignment problem without a backward pass. In *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 4937–4955. PMLR, 2022.
- [2] X. Yi. Asymptotic Singular Value Distribution of Linear Convolutional Layers. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:2006.07117, June 2020. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2006.07117.